

Innovation Definition
Comparative assessment
(EN)

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The paper was designed for a collaborative cooperation work on the intellectual property creation model.

The wish of the author is to try to create the discussion on the paper. If the discussion on the paper could be achieved the author would like to expand its **contents** in the several fields:

- ✎ dynamic change of the innovation phenomena (linear vs. present approach)
- ✎ innovation definition and in particularly measuring the innovation
- ✎ chapter describing how the modern innovation model can be evaluated on the example of the viable project proposal (e.g. in regards to EU 6'th framework programme <https://cordis.europa.eu/>)

The content creation process would be the trial simulation of the intellectual value creation, using the network model. Any suggestions within the substantial comments provision are welcomed. **Any user is welcome to contribute to the content creation work.**

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Innovation Definition

Comparative assessment

1. Theory of Innovation – general view on the innovation

Though the importance of the innovation is increasing these days there is a big difficulty in its understanding. There exists a clear anxiety through out the academic world as to the way of defining it. The definition and the theory of innovation though, seem to be so important in the days of the knowledge economy and high-tech driven economic growth, that the wish for understanding it, demands precise and as objective as possible definition.

Innovation problems theorist James M. Utterback once wrote: *“The innovation research theory matter is highly dispersed. It was not adopted by any of the science fields. (...) There is no sufficient data set, for building innovation prediction model”*.²

With creation 2000 Lisbon agenda the innovation becomes a crucial way of achieving high economic development and growth. There seem to be a need for introducing as objective as possible innovation definition.

When in the 1911, Joseph Schumpeter published for the first time “The theory of Economic Development”³, he described the motor of the development as the innovation itself. The innovation was not well defined by that time but it was clearly described in his proceeding works in which he used the innovation term.

According to Peter F. Drucker innovation can be generally defined as: the process of equipping in new, improved capabilities or increased utility. It is worth saying that innovation is not a science or technology but a value which can be measured with environmental impact. According to Drucker’s theory it has to be market oriented and if it is product oriented it will create a “technology miracle” without creating required benefits.⁵

² J. M. Utterback (1986), *Innovation and Corporate Strategy*, International Journal of Technology Management, vol. 1

³ Schumpeter, J. (1934), *The Theory of Economic Development*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

According to the Peter Drucker, J. Schumpeter was the economist who focused his studies on the entrepreneurship and its impact on the economy. The norm for the healthy economy and basis for its theory and practice should not be balance and optimisation but dynamic ⁴imbalance caused by the innovation implementing enterprises. This temporary imbalance is seen as the only way of economic development. Development is created by the “*creative destruction*”, by temporary destruction of balance.⁵

J. Shumpeter stressed non static character of the development which is not likely to arise from schematic mechanisms and optimised, balanced processes.⁶

Peter Drucker wrote, that from the business management point of view there are only two main tasks: marketing and innovation. Whereas the marketing function is to satisfy current needs of the consumers, innovation goes further to satisfy consumers future needs. Without an ability for constant innovation, enterprise disappears in the moment when the consumers needs, technology or competition are changed. In the last decade pace of changes is constantly accelerating. In the business sector innovation is often used as a strategic factor of the competition.

2. Characteristics of the innovation

Before introducing the definition of the innovation, the distinction between innovation and invention is important to make. Invention is the first occurrence of an idea for a new product or process, while the innovation is the first attempt to carry it out into practise.

In other words invention is a new product, where as innovation is a new value.

While inventions can be carried out anywhere, for example in the universities, innovations occur mostly in firms, though they may also occur in other types of the organizations. To be able to turn invention into innovation a firm normally needs to combine several different types of

⁴ Drucker Peter F. (1974), Management. Tasks, Responsibilities, Practices, Harper & Row

⁵ Drucker Peter. F. (1985), Innovation and Entrepreneurship, Harper and Row, New York

⁶ Schumpeter, J. (1934), The Theory of Economic Development, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

knowledge, capabilities, skills and resources. For instance, the firm may require production knowledge, skills and facilities, market knowledge, a well functioning distribution system, sufficient financial resources, etc.

One of the strongest characteristics of the innovation show the innovation is a continuous process – innovation is often an effect of the small incremental/ marginal changes in the product or process. A long lags between innovation and invention, being an affect of lacking proper conditions for commercial implementation makes the difference between innovation and invention distinctive.⁷

Following the understanding the innovation as crucial for economic change, “radical” innovations shape big changes in the world, whereas “incremental” fill in the process of change continuously.⁹

3. Innovation dynamo – sources of the innovation

The European Commission⁸ in its communication stresses the importance of the source of the innovation in regards to its definition. The source of the innovation can be described as the system of factors shaping innovation at the firm level and is referred as the “*innovation dynamo*”¹¹. There are several ways for the innovation to be created:

- It may be in the form of invention. (...) Research is a major contributor to innovation, generating a flow of technical ideas and continually renewing the pool of technical skills.
- An enterprise may be innovative by taking an idea from another business sector and adapting it for use in its own production processes or market.
- The search for new, untapped, market space is another driving force. This may rely on technological innovation or on reconfiguring existing products and services so as to present a radical change that will be perceived by customers as offering more or better value (“value innovation”).

⁷ Fagerberg Jan (2004), The Oxford Handbook of Innovation, Oxford University Press, Oxford, New York ⁹ Schumpeter, J. (1934), The Theory of Economic Development, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

⁸ COM (2003) 112 final

- It may be through introduction of a comprehensively new approach to a business, such as new business models of on-line retailers, with the objective of creating new market space or increasing profitability in an existing market.

The OECD (1997), Oslo Manual systematised this approach dividing the source of innovation or in another words options open to a firm which wants to innovate into three groups: *strategic*, *R&D* and *non-R&D*:

- Strategic: decisions concerning the types of market to serve, or create, and types of innovations to attempt there.
- R&D: R&D in the *Frascati Manual*¹² sense, including experimental development that goes beyond and applied research:
 - basic research for expanding knowledge about fundamental processes related to the production processes in the firm;
 - strategic research (research with industrial relevance but no specific application) to broaden the range of applied projects that are open to the firm, and applied research to produce specific inventions or modifications of existing techniques;
 - develop product concepts to judge whether they are feasible and viable, a stage which involves: i) prototype design; ii) development and testing; and iii) further research to modify designs or technical functions.
- non-R&D: activities that do not have straight forward relation to R&D, and are not defined as R&D, yet play a major role in corporate innovation and performance:
 - identification of the new product concepts and production technologies: i) via marketing side and relations with users; ii) via the identification of the opportunities for commercialization resulting from firm's own or others' basic or strategic research iii) via design and engineering capabilities; iv) by monitoring competitors; v) by using consultants;
 - development of pilot and then full scale facilities;
 - purchase of technical information, paying fees and royalties for patented inventions (which usually require research and engineering work to adopt and modify), or buy know-how and skills through engineering and design consultancy of various types;
 - human skills relevant to the production can be developed (through internal training) or purchase (by hiring) or tacit and informal training – “learn – by – doing”

- investing in process equipment or intermediate inputs which embody the innovative work of others (components, machines or entire plant);

¹¹ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

¹² OECD (2002), The Measurement of Scientific and Technological Activities, Proposed Standard Practise for Surveys on Research and Experimental Development, Frascati Manual

- management systems, production system and its methods reorganisation including new types of inventory management and quality control, and continuous quality improvement.

4. Definitions of the Innovation

In his work on economic development J. Schumpeter distinguished between five different types of innovation:

- new products
- new methods of production
- new sources of supply
- the exploration of new market
- new ways to organize business

Most of the definitions focus on the first two of these: *new products* and *methods of production (processes)* as the most distinctive ones for the purpose economic impact analysis of the innovation.

The argument for focusing particularly on the distinction between product and process innovation often rests on the assumption that their economic and social impact may differ. While the introduction of new product is commonly assumed to have a clear, positive effect on growth of income and employment, it has been argued that process innovation, due to its cost-cutting nature, may have more ambiguous effect.⁹

From the private sector, managerial point of view innovation can be defined as a: *development and creation of new or improved, in consumer understanding, products or services. The pro*

⁹ Fagerberg Jan (2004), The Oxford Handbook of Innovation, Oxford University Press, Oxford, New York

*innovation conditions under that definition are created by the changes which impose new consumer needs or offer solutions for existing needs.*¹⁰

In accordance with the communication of the European Commission COM(1995) 688, consistent with the Lisbon European Council's perception of the innovation and competitiveness, innovation is *"the renewal and enlargement of the range of products and services and associated markets; the establishment of new methods of production, supply and distribution; the introduction in changes in management, work organization, and the working conditions and skills of workforce."*¹¹

For the purpose of statistics more harmonised product and process innovation definition was introduced. It was proposed by the OECD, European Commission and Eurostat in the guidelines for collecting and interpreting technological innovation data (Oslo Manual).

*Technological product and process (TPP) innovations comprise implemented technologically new products and processes and significant technological improvements in products and processes. A TPP innovation has been implemented if it has been introduced on the market (product innovation) or used within a production process (process innovation). TPP innovations involve a series of scientific, technological, organisational, financial and commercial activities. The TPP innovating firm is one that has implemented technologically new or significantly technologically improved products or processes during the period under review.*¹² This definition is called Technological Product and Process (TPP) definition, and is a base framework for innovation definitions in the EU states.

According to the National Institute of Standards and Technology, an agency of the U.S. Commerce Department's Technology Administration¹³, we can distinguish between two types of innovation: technological and commercial. *Technological innovation is the successful implementation (in commerce or management) of a technical idea new to the institution creating it. A commercial innovation is the result of the application of technical, market, or business-*

¹⁰ Peter Doyle, (1998), *Marketing, Management and Strategy*, Prentice Hall Europe

¹¹ COM (1995) 688

¹² OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

¹³ <http://www.atp.nist.gov>

*model ingenuity to create a new or improved product, process, or service that is successfully introduced into the market.*¹⁴

The broad US innovation definition which could be compared in the most appropriate way with the OECD and European Union definition was created by the 21st Century Innovation Working Group in the National Innovation Initiative paper (2004). It states that: *Innovation is a process through which the nation creates and transforms new knowledge into useful products, services and processes for national and global markets – leading to both value creation for stakeholders and higher standards of living.*¹⁵

5. Innovation definition analysis framework

As previous chapters show though innovation definitions may overlap in the semantics sense, there is no one consistent meaning and understanding of the innovation. The definition approach varies from very broad to more narrow sense, used mostly for the research and quantitative measurement purposes (indicators). These different approaches capture different factors of the innovation, depending on the problem being concerted.

In the paper for an effective comparison several innovation definitions were analysed. The definitions were grouped into three categories: *European Union definition, OECD definition and US definition.*

Each of the definition has been analysed by taking into the consideration several factors: 1) *object of the definition*, 2) *process showed in the definition*, 3) *subject of the definition*, 4) *results/output*, 5) *timeframe of the processes defined.*

By an **object of the innovation** definition we mean a focus of attention through which the innovation process is being implemented. Some of the definitions focus primary on technological innovations, but there are also ones that include organisational and presentational

¹⁴ Institute of Standards and Technology (2003), *Between Invention and Innovation, an Analysis of Funding for Early-Stage Technology Development*, NIST GCR 02–841, <http://www.atp.nist.gov/eao/gcr02-841/chapt2.htm>

¹⁵ Council on Competitiveness, Donofrio Nick (2004), *21th century Innovation Working Group Final Report, Innovation The new reality for national Prosperity*, National Innovation Initiative, Washington DC ²⁰ Schumpeter, J. (1934), *The Theory of Economic Development*, Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Massachusetts.

innovation of a product or service. Generally the object of the innovation is defined as *product /service, process, or strategy*. The broadest approach of that problem and basis for most of the innovation definitions was introduced by J. Schumpeter.²⁰

Process of the innovation implementation can be generally defined as: a series of actions, changes, or functions bringing about a result; or series of operations performed in the making or treatment of a product. For the purpose of this paper this definition element was broadly defined as: *new implementations or improvements*.

Subject of the innovation is an entity, by which the purpose of the innovation is indicated, i.e. is a recipient of the innovation for who the innovation validation criteria is made (importance, validity of the innovation factors), or in other words is the target of the diffusion innovation process. Some of definitions distinguish between firm level, regional or worldwide innovation others between innovations in different types of sectors, but it also can be broken down for instance by operating market (new to the operating market) or by geographical area (new to the country or region, of policy interest), for example: *firms (private sector); organizations (private, public and non-governmental sectors defined horizontally); public sector organizations; regional, nation-wide or world wide (economy/markets/ society)*.

Result or output of the innovation is a feature that is not broadly introduced into the innovation definitions. Innovation result or output defines the way and extent that innovation will have its effect or impact. It is (or should be) strictly connected with the subject of the innovation definition. Among the innovation definitions there is no rule and recurrence in defining this element, but mostly it has a qualitative character (*higher standard of living, economic growth, etc.*).

Time frame of the innovation definition is usually omitted in the general innovation definitions. Time frame of the innovation is a period during which the innovation takes place or is projected to occur. Most harmonised narrow definitions such as Oslo Manual¹⁶ definition precise time frame as *the period under review*.

Figure 1 describes definition elements and relations between them.

¹⁶ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

Figure 1
Innovation definition analysis

6. Innovation definition analysis

The most comprehensive framework for the innovation definition harmonisation was done by the OECD and European Commission of the European Union. There also exists some work in that issue done by the federal government of the United States of America, but it is more of the innovation policy definition and has a character of the policy postulates. It is important to say that besides the “big” general framework created on the central level (EU, OECD, US governments) there also exist “smaller” national or state innovation frameworks, supported by the central level government initiatives.²²

6.1. European Union and OECD innovation definition

The harmonised innovation definition was introduced in 1997 by the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), Eurostat and European Commission. It was included in the document called Oslo Manual “*The measurement of Scientific and technological activities, proposed guidelines for collecting and interpreting technological innovation data*”.

As an **object of the innovation** the Oslo Manual paper concentrates on the Technological Product and Process innovation definition. The term “product” is used to cover both goods and services.

Non Technological Product and Process innovation such as organisational and managerial innovations were excluded from the definition. These types of innovation are only included if they occur as the part of some technological innovation project. The organisational change is only counted as a technological change when there is a measurable change in the firm’s output, either production or sales. Purely organisational change is not included in technological change.

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Process of the innovation implementation in the harmonised definition is seen as complete action of *new implementation* or *improvements* of the TPP.

A technologically new means that, technological characteristics or intended uses differ significantly from those of previously produced products or processes. Such innovations can involve radically new technologies, can be based on combining existing technologies in new uses, or can be derived from the use of new knowledge.

A technologically improved means that existing performance has been significantly enhanced or upgraded. A simple product or process may be improved (in terms of better performance or lower cost) through use of higher-performance components or materials or a complex product/ process

²² For the EU regional innovation initiatives please visit: <http://www.cordis.lu/regions/> For the US national regional initiative please visit: <http://www.compete.org/nri/>

²³ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

which consists of a number of integrated technical sub-systems may be improved by partial changes to one of the sub-systems.¹⁷

Subject of the innovation indicates on what level the innovation diffusion occurs.

Worldwide TPP innovation occurs when a new or improved product or process is implemented at the very first time. *Firm-only* TPP innovation occurs when a firm implements a new or improved product or process which is technologically novel for the unit concerned but is already implemented in other firms and industries. The Oslo Manual harmonised (OECD-EU) definition covers all these levels as the minimum entry level is “new to the firm”.¹⁸ It is worth mentioning that the definition focuses on the private –sector – firm as a subject of the definition. Although the definition intention seems to have a horizontal meaning (all sectors included), the term “firm” indicates private sector – focus excluding other types of organizations.

Results of the innovation are not included in the harmonised definition framework. The OECD-UE definitions are not result oriented.

The timeframe of the innovation implementation seems to be an important factor of the definition. The time frame in the harmonised (OECD-EU) innovation definition is defined as the *period under review*.

The relationship between the subject and object of the innovation is covered by the Oslo Manual definition, as shown in Figure 2.

¹⁷ *ibid.*

¹⁸ *ibid.*

Figure 2
Type and degree of novelty and the definition of innovation Source: OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

			INNOVATION			<i>Not Innovation</i>
			Maximum	Intermediate	Minimum	
			New to the world	(a)	New to the firm	
INNOVATION	Technologically new	Product				
		Production process				
		Delivery process				
	Significantly technologically improved	Product				
		Production process				
		Delivery process				
Other Innovation	New or improved	Purely organisation				
<i>Not Innovation</i>	No Significant change,	Product				
		Production process				
	Change without novelty,	Delivery process				
		Creative improvements	Purely organisation			

TPP innovation Other innovation Not innovation

(a) Could be geographical e.g. new to the country or region

6.2.US Innovation definition

There is no one consistent framework towards US government innovation definition. The literature concentrates on the functions, role and the effect of the innovation in economic terms rather than approaching the subject in academic definition way.

Important framework in that issue was presented by the US Department of Commerce, Institute of Standards and Technology,¹⁹ and the latest innovation policy developments produced by the National Innovation Initiative.²⁰ Conclusions and summary points shown in this work concern these two policy papers.

Object of the innovation is defined very generally as product, process or service. The Technological innovation definition is stressing the importance of the *technical idea* as the source and more general entity to product, process, and service.

Process of the innovation is shown as the successful implementation of application or new knowledge transformation and creation. There always are two elements of the process: new implementation or modification (improvement, transformation). In the 21' century innovation working group definition *idem per idem* logic error occurs: the process is described as a process itself.²⁸

In the first broad definition the **subject of the innovation** is characterised here as: as *national and global markets*. The second approach perceive subject as an *institution*. Both approaches (more general and institution based) seem to stress the economic function of the innovation i.e. its potential marketable applicability.

The US based definition seems to be **results oriented**. The definition states that the innovation process *leads to both value creation for stakeholders and higher standards of living*. Second set of the narrow definition stress the condition under which the implementation is done – it must be a successful implementation (market or management). By these definitions the innovation is as marketable result of the process which creates the socioeconomic impact.

There is no **time frame** set in the definitions. It means that the process of the innovation does not have the time reference.

¹⁹ Institute of Standards and Technology (2003), Between Invention and Innovation, an Analysis of Funding for Early-Stage Technology Development, NIST GCR 02–841, <http://www.atp.nist.gov/ea0/gcr02-841/chapt2.htm>

²⁰ Council on Competitiveness, Donofrio Nick (2004), 21th century Innovation Working Group Final Report, Innovation The new reality for national Prosperity, National Innovation Initiative, Washington DC ²⁸ This type of definition error occurs when defined object is being defined by itself. The innovation here is defined as: a *process through which the nation creates and transforms new knowledge into useful products*,

7. Conclusions of the definition analysis - the comparison

The comparison shows that although the definitions overlap to some extent they keep different general point of attention. The harmonised OECD- UE definition is a very narrow based designed for the measurement purposes and statistics. Its main characteristic is that it uses Technological Product and Process as a definition object.

The meaning of the label “technological”, as applied to products and processes, and its precise scope in surveys and studies, can be unclear. This is particularly true in an international context. It is not always easy to distinguish between the special meaning attributed here, the dictionary definitions of the word (or its nearest equivalent in some languages) which may differ subtly between countries, and the overtones of the word to which respondents may react. For example, it was felt that in the service industries “technological” might be understood as “using high-tech plant and equipment”.²⁹

In contrary to the US definition it is not result oriented (its purpose is to serve as a basis of innovation output analysis). The US definitions have more of the policy statement character. They are result oriented and perceive the object and the process of the definition in more general way.

General conclusion can be drawn that definition framework concentrate on the economic (market) aspect of the innovation. Even though the definition is not result oriented (does not state the necessity of the innovation economic impact) it seeks it in at the end. The US distinction between technological innovation and market innovation and purpose of the OECD-EU innovation definition shows it clearly.

The purpose of defining innovation is to set a clear set of tools as a way for capturing it as an economic phenomenon, what could lead eventually to socio-economic impact assessment analysis (at the micro and macro economic level). The measurement toolset can be applied to the (classical) linear innovation process (R&D, patent creation analysis), but more importantly

*services and **processes** for national and global markets – leading to both value creation for stakeholders and higher standards of living.* ²⁹ OECD (1997), Oslo Manual

network models, manifested by spillovers and inter-sector knowledge exchange. The task for measuring innovation is very complex and fragile problem.

Figure 3
Innovation Definition Comparison Matrix

	EU	US	OECD
Object			
Technological Product (goods and services) and Process (TPP)	X		X
Generally: Product and Process	X*	X	
Not defined			
Process			
New implementations	X	X (creation)	X
Improvements	X	X (transformation)	X
Not defined			
Subject			
The firm (private sector)	X		X
The institution (organization)		X	
World-wide	X	X (nation)	X
Not defined			
Results			
Value creation for stakeholders		X	
Higher standard of living		X	
General economic growth		X	
Not Defined	X		X
Time frame			
Defined (period under review)	X		X
Not defined	X*	X	

*Communications of European Commission

Figure 3 and 4 indicate correlation between the features in the innovation definitions.

Figure 4
INNOVATION DEFINITION MATRIX

DEFINITION (source)	Object			Process			Subject				Results				Timeframe	
	Technological Product goods and services) and Process (TPP)	Generally Product and Process	Not defined	New implementations	Improvements	Not defined	The firm	The institution organization)	World-wide	Not defined	Value creation for stakeholders, higher standard of living	General economic growth	General product application	Not Defined	Defined (period under review)	Not defined
Community rules on state aid for innovation SEC(2004) 1453	X			X	X		X							X	X	
European Innovation Scoreboard 2004 European Commission COM (1995) 688 (Green Paper on Innovation)		X		X	X				X					X		X
COM (2003) 112 final		X		X	X			X						X		X
Innovation in FP7 INFSO Position Paper (2004)		X		X	X		X	X						X		X
Polish Ministry of Economic Affairs and Labour (2000)	X			X	X				X					X		X
Oslo Manual (1997)	X			X	X		X							X	X	
NII 21 st Century Innovation Working Group (2004)		X		X	X			X		X	X					X
US Department of Commerce NIST GCR 02-841 (2003)		X		X	X			X				X				X

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